

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF EXISTING FARMINGSYSTEMS IN WESTERN MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract

The present investigation was carried out on the economics of existing farming systems in Western Maharashtra. The results revealed that, at overall level, the per hectare gross returns were ₹ 1,59,090, ₹ 3,86,841, and ₹ 6,70,776 for farming system I, II, and III, respectively. The cost 'C' at overall level were ₹ 1,29,453, ₹ 2,78,122 and ₹ 4,10,113 for farming system I, II and III, respectively. The net returns at cost 'C' at overall level were found to be ₹ 29,637, ₹ 1,08,719 and ₹ 2,60,663 for farming system I, II and III, respectively. The output-input ratios were to be obtained 1.23, 1.39 and 1.63 for farming system I, II and III, respectively. Results indicated that the farming system III was found more profitable than farming system II and farming system II was found more profitable than farming system I. The farming systems in irrigated region were found more profitable than farming systems in rainfed region. Hence it is concluded that, farming system III was most beneficial farming system due to diversification and assurance of farm income. At the overall level per hectare total employment generated was higher in farming system III (383.13 mandays) as compared to farming system II (264.61 mandays) and farming system I (134.76 mandays). The total income of per farms were worked out to be ₹ 3,21,584, ₹ 6,15,944 and ₹ 16,26,965 in farming system I, II and III, respectively. The average per farm total expenditures of the sample farms were ₹ 2,76,726 ; ₹ 5,21,908 and ₹ 11,21,907 in farming systems I, II, and III, respectively.

The study found that farming systems II (Crops + Livestock) and III (Crops + Livestock + Horticulture) are suitable for the Western Maharashtra region because it provides more sustainable productivity and profitability, resource recycling and replacing, and maximum net returns per unit land area. They also provide employment for the farm family throughout the year.

Keywords: Farming systems, Profitability, Employment, Income and Expenditure (Arial, inclined, 10 fonts, justified)

Introduction

The current agricultural scenario in India is characterized by high input costs, fluctuations in market prices, and the risk of crop loss due to climatic and biotic factors. This highlights the need for a farming systems approach. Environmental degradation, soil fertility depletion, unstable farmer income, and low standards of living are additional factors that increase the importance of this approach.

The income from cropping alone on small and marginal farms is hardly sufficient to sustain the farmer's family with the decline in farm size (0.15 ha. /person) due to explosion of population and this situation gets further weakened due to failure of monsoon. It is, therefore essential that farmers should adopt different farming systems or subsidiary enterprises like diary, poultry, horticulture, goat rearing, sericulture, fishery etc. in their crop production programme for generation of regular and evenly distributed income throughout the year (Dorge, 2009 ; Tayde, 2015).

It is emerging that livestock and horticulture are the two major subsectors which can drive maximum potential growth required for doubling the farmers' incomes. The non-traditional areas for cultivation can provide a remunerative solution for further enhancing the farmers' income. These may include shifting orientation from cereal dominance to high value crops (HVC) like horticulture and livestock. Integrated farming is one of the solutions for enhancing the income and gains to farmers (Saxena, 2017).

The farming system is defined as a combination of crops or a mix of enterprises, where the product and byproduct of one enterprise serve as input for another. The focus is on the system as a whole, rather than just its overall output. The concept of farming systems is similar the concept of Integrated farming systems (IFS), where integration of various farming system or various enterprises takes place.

The study "Economic analysis of existing farming systems in Western Maharashtra" assessed the economic viability of various farming systems in the region. It analyzes farming systems combining crop production, livestock, and horticulture, focusing on socio-economic aspects and sustainability. The study's main objective is to economically evaluate these systems, exploring resource use efficiency, profitability, costs, returns, employment, and constraints. The present paper presents the profitability, employment, income and expenditure of selected farming systems in Western Maharashtra.

Material And Methods

For the present study, the primary data was obtained by survey method from the selected farmers with the aid of specially designed questionnaire for the year 2019-20. Primary data for 240 farmers was obtained using a personal interview method. The data was collected on many elements such as the family size, land use, cropping pattern, capital assets, livestock position, cost and returns from Crop only, Crop + Livestock and Crop + Livestock + Horticulture. Using proper statistical methods, the data collected from cultivators were tabulated and analyzed. The profitability, employment, income and expenditure of farming systems were examined in order to meet the study's objectives. On per hectare basis, different farming systems were compared in terms of income received, expenditure incurred and employment patterns.

Results And Discussion**Profitability of selected farming systems**

The per hectare gross returns were ₹ 1,59,090, ₹ 3,86,841, and ₹ 6,70,776 for farming system I, II, and III, respectively (Table 1). The cost 'C' at overall level were ₹ 1,29,453, ₹ 2,78,122 and ₹ 4,10,113 for farming system I, II and III, respectively. The output-input ratios were to be obtained 1.23, 1.39 and 1.63 for farming system I, II and III, respectively. The gross returns were more in farming system III due to the high return from horticulture activity. Horticultural crops, such as vegetables and fruits, have a higher market value than cereal crops. Horticulture is a more intensive farming system than crop farming. This means that it requires more inputs, such as fertilizers, pesticides, and water.

In farming system III is more profitable in the irrigated region than in the rainfed region. This is because the higher yields in the irrigated region offset the higher cost of cultivation. This is because the yields of the crops are higher in the irrigated region. The higher cost of cultivation in farming system III is offset by the higher returns from horticulture.

It is concluded that all the farming systems were profitable in the selected area. Although farming system III (Crops + livestock+ Horticulture) was found more profitable than farming system II (Crops + livestock), and farming system II was found more profitable than farming system I (Crops only). The net returns of irrigated as well as rainfed region for all farming system I, II and III were positive and different from each other's.

Per hectare employment pattern

At the overall level, per hectare total employment on sample farms was highest in farming system III (383.13 mandays), followed by farming system II (264.61 mandays) and farming system I (134.76 mandays). The higher per hectare employment in farming system III is due to the more labor intensive nature of this farming system. Farming system III involves the cultivation of horticultural crops, which require more labor than cereal crops.

This indicates that farming system I generate less employment as compared to other farming systems. The employment is not provided throughout the year, hence the farmer family has to find employment in other activities than only cultivation of crops. This can be a challenge for farmers, especially in rural areas where there may be limited opportunities for off-farm employment. On the other hand in farming system-II and III employment generated was comparatively more as compared to farming system I. Due to more enterprises in farming system III, it was able to provide more employment throughout year. Comparatively, employment in irrigated region was more than rainfed region in all farming systems, because in irrigated regions, crops like sugarcane, fruits, and vegetables require more labor.

Income pattern of selected farming systems

The total income of per farms at the overall level was worked out to be ₹ 3,21,584, ₹ 6,15,944 and ₹ 16,26,965 in farming system I, II and III, respectively.

In farming system I, 26.65 per cent of the income was derived from other than farm business activity. In farming systems II and III, 5.17 per cent and 1.68 per cent of the income, respectively, was derived from other than farm business activity. This indicates that farming system I depends more on other than farm business activity than farming systems II and III.

The total income in farming system-II was twice that of farming system I, while the total income of farming system III was five times that of farming system I. The total income from farming system-I (crop production) was much lower than that of farming systems II and III. More than 50 per cent of the income in farming system I was derived from crop production, while nearly 50 per cent of the income in farming system II was derived from crop production. While in farming system-III, nearly 50 per cent income was derived from horticulture. The results obtained were in line with the studies conducted by Alagumani and Anjugam (2000), Sharma et al. (2021), Paramesh *et al.* (2022), and Dorge *et al.* (2022).

Expenditure pattern of selected farming systems

The average per farm total expenditure of the sample farms were ₹ 2,76,726 ; ₹ 5,21,908 and ₹ 11,21,907 in farming systems I, II, and III, respectively. Out of that, more than 70 per cent was from the farm expenditure in all the three farming systems. The expenditure on crop production was the major expenditure in farming system I and II, while expenditure on horticulture was the major expenditure in farming system III, due to the higher costs of fruit and vegetables cultivation. In farming system II and III, farmer has expenditure requirement for maintenance of livestock. It includes expenditure of feed and fodder, medical expenditure etc. The region wise total expenditure was more in irrigated region than the rainfed region; this means that farmers in irrigated region can produce more crops and livestock, which leads to higher income.

The income and expenditure patterns in farming system I show that farm business income was more than total expenditure in the irrigated region, but less than total expenditure (farm+ family) in the rainfed region. Farmers in both regions need to supplement their income from other sources, such as off-farm employment or government assistance, in order to meet their family's needs. In both regions of farming system I, farmers have to supplement their family expenditure needs from

income sources other than farming, as farm income alone is not sufficient to meet their needs. However, in farming systems II and III, family expenditure can be met from farm income alone. Hence, it can be concluded that farming systems II and III are more sustainable than farming system I because they combine multiple components that can increase productivity. These findings confirmed the results reported by Dorge (2010) and Singh *et al.* (2013).

Conclusion

For the study area, all the farming systems of irrigated as well as rainfed region were economically viable, while farming systems of irrigated regions were more economically viable than farming systems of rainfed region. The farmers of farming systems II and III in both regions had an economic surplus because both regions had sustainable farm income. Farming system I could manage to get some additional returns than costs but they are hardly sufficient fulfill livelihood needs of the farming families. The study found that farming systems II and III are suitable for the western Maharashtra region because they provide more sustainable productivity and profitability, resource recycling and replacing, and maximum net returns per unit land area. They also provide employment for the farm family throughout the year.

Authors' Contributions

'Author A' designed the study, performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. 'Author B' and 'Author C' managed the analyses of the study. 'Author C' managed the literature searches..... All authors read and approved the final manuscript."

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Table 1 Per hectare Cost and returns structure of sample farms

(Per ha.)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Farming System-I (Crops Only)			Farming System-II (Crops + Livestock)			Farming System-III (Crops + Livestock+ Horti.)		
		Irrigated	Rainfed	Overall	Irrigated	Rainfed	Overall	Irrigated	Rainfed	Overall
1	Gross Returns (₹)	217445	100735	159090	515777	257906	386841	875157	466394	670776
2	Cost 'A'(₹)	80423	44453	62438	131322	90901	111111	188170	135866	162018
3	Cost 'B'(₹)	158134	85038	121586	281532	165694	223613	396737	287783	342260
5	Cost 'C'(₹)	168418	90488	129453	345901	210343	278122	476469	343756	410113
6	Profits at Cost 'A'(₹)	137022	56282	96652	384455	167005	275730	686987	330528	508758
7	Profits at Cost 'B'(₹)	59311	15697	37504	234245	92212	163228	478420	178611	328516
8	Net returns at Cost 'C'(₹)	49027	10247	29637	169876	47563	108719	398688	122638	260663
9	Output Input Ratio	1.29	1.11	1.23	1.49	1.23	1.39	1.84	1.36	1.63

Table 2. Per hectare employment pattern of sample farms (Per ha.)

Sr. No.	Particulars		Farming Systems I (Crops only)			Farming Systems II (Crops +Livestock)			Farming Systems III (Crops +Livestock +Horti.)		
			Irrigated	Rainfed	Overall	Irrigated	Rainfed	Overall	Irrigated	Rainfed	Overall
Crop production											
1	a. Male	Owned	39.10	20.57	29.84	38.93	28.88	33.90	22.97	15.62	19.30
		Hired	46.65	11.99	29.32	39.95	13.83	26.89	27.27	14.50	20.89
	b. Female	Owned	12.96	19.30	16.13	31.27	34.14	32.70	12.25	7.55	9.90
		Hired	73.35	35.01	54.18	61.41	36.35	48.88	39.08	26.71	32.90
	Subtotal			172.07 (96.89)	86.87 (94.49)	129.47 (96.07)	171.57 (52.16)	113.19 (56.51)	142.38 (53.81)	101.58 (22.14)	64.39 (20.94)
Livestock											
2	a. Male	Owned	5.52	5.07	5.29	58.34	30.01	44.17	53.74	38.30	46.02
	b. Female		-	-	-	99.01	57.11	78.06	113.17	52.82	83.00
	Subtotal			5.52 (3.11)	5.07 (5.51)	5.29 (3.93)	157.35 (47.84)	87.12 (43.49)	122.24 (46.19)	166.91 (36.38)	91.12 (29.64)
Horticulture											
3	a. Male	Owned	-	-	-	-	-	-	61.92	56.27	59.09
		Hired	-	-	-	-	-	-	53.08	37.64	45.36
	b. Female	Owned	-	-	-	-	-	-	37.04	28.23	32.64
		Hired	-	-	-	-	-	-	38.26	29.80	34.03
	Subtotal			-	-	-	-	-	-	190.30 (41.48)	151.95 (49.42)
Grand total											
4	a. Male	Owned	44.62	25.64	35.13	97.27	58.88	78.08	138.63	110.20	124.41
		Hired	46.65	11.99	29.32	39.95	13.83	26.89	80.35	52.15	66.25
	b. Female	Owned	12.96	19.30	16.13	130.28	91.25	110.76	162.47	88.60	125.53
		Hired	73.35	35.01	54.18	61.41	36.35	48.88	77.35	56.52	66.93

	Total Employment (Own + Hired)	177.59 (100)	91.94 (100)	134.76 (100)	328.92 (100)	200.31 (100)	264.61 (100)	458.80 (100)	307.46 (100)	383.13 (100)
	Total Owned Employment	57.58	44.94	51.26	227.55	150.13	188.84	301.10	198.79	249.95

(Figures in parentheses are percentages to the total)

Table 3 Income pattern of selected farming systems

(Per farm)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Farming systems I (Crops only)			Farming systems II (Crops+ Livestock)			Farming systems III (Crops+ Livestock+ Hort.)		
		Irrigated	Rainfed	Overall	Irrigated	Rainfed	Overall	Irrigated	Rainfed	Overall
1	Crop production	315234 (78.73)	145190 (59.80)	230212 (71.59)	356442 (44.15)	185373 (43.66)	270908 (43.98)	458811 (22.03)	209793 (17.91)	334302 (20.55)
2	Dairy (Milk /Manures)	4411 (1.10)	6921 (2.85)	5666 (1.76)	405820 (50.27)	205820 (48.48)	305820 (49.65)	566572 (27.20)	350358 (29.91)	458465 (28.18)
3	Poultry / Goats	-	-	-	11403 (1.41)	3403 (0.80)	7403 (1.20)	40357 (1.94)	54814 (4.68)	47586 (2.92)
4	Horticulture Production	-	-	-	-	-	-	990879 (47.58)	527699 (45.06)	759289 (46.67)
Farm business income		319645 (79.83)	152111 (62.66)	235878 (73.35)	773665 (95.83)	394596 (92.95)	584131 (94.83)	2056620 (98.75)	1142664 (97.56)	1599642 (98.32)
5	Other sources									
	a) Wages	45725 (11.42)	61363 (25.28)	53544 (16.65)	12050 (1.49)	18626 (4.39)	15338 (2.49)	4556 (0.22)	12890 (1.10)	8723 (0.54)
	b) Business / Service	35025 (8.75)	29300 (12.07)	32163 (10.00)	21626 (2.68)	11325 (2.67)	16476 (2.67)	21550 (1.03)	15650 (1.34)	18600 (1.14)
Income from other sources		80750 (20.17)	90663 (37.34)	85706 (26.65)	33676 (4.17)	29951 (7.05)	31814 (5.17)	26106 (1.25)	28540 (2.44)	27323 (1.68)
Total Income		400395 (100)	242774 (100)	321584 (100)	807341 (100)	424547 (100)	615944 (100)	2082726 (100)	1171204 (100)	1626965 (100)

(Figures in parentheses are percentages to the total income)

Table 4 Expenditure patterns selected farming systems (Per farm)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Farming system I (Crops only)			Farming system II (Crops +Livestock)			Farming system III (Crops+ Livestock+ Horticulture)		
		Irrigated	Rainfed	Overall	Irrigated	Rainfed	Overall	Irrigated	Rainfed	Overall
1	Crop production	245396 (72.87)	134752 (62.18)	190074 (68.69)	339249 (53.87)	172130 (41.57)	255689 (48.99)	310829 (24.44)	164903 (16.96)	237866 (21.20)
2	Livestock / Poultry	2179 (0.65)	1886 (0.87)	2032 (0.73)	179560 (28.51)	149668 (36.15)	164614 (31.54)	356961 (28.07)	303193 (31.19)	330077 (29.42)
3	Horticulture	-	-	-	-	-	-	451912 (35.53)	374106 (38.49)	413009 (36.81)
Farm expenditure		247575 (73.52)	136637 (63.05)	192106 (69.42)	518808 (82.38)	321798 (77.72)	420303 (80.53)	1119702 (88.04)	842202 (86.64)	980952 (87.44)
4		48690	43950	46320	55440	50070	52755	73410	60840	67125

	A. Food (Foodgrains, oils, vegetables, etc.)	(14.46)	(20.28)	(16.74)	(8.80)	(12.09)	(10.11)	(5.77)	(6.26)	(5.98)
	B. Non food expenditure	40490 (12.02)	36110 (16.66)	38300 (13.84)	55530 (8.82)	42170 (10.19)	48850 (9.36)	78630 (6.18)	69030 (7.10)	73830 (6.58)
	Family expenditure	89180 (26.48)	80060 (36.95)	84620 (30.58)	110970 (17.62)	92240 (22.28)	101605 (19.47)	152040 (11.96)	129870 (13.36)	140955 (12.56)
5	Total expenditure (Farm+ Family)	336755 (100)	216697 (100)	276726 (100)	629778 (100)	414038 (100)	521908 (100)	1271742 (100)	972072 (100)	1121907 (100)

(Figures in parentheses are percentages to the total expenditure)